

NBSINFRA

Funded by the
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City lab Booklet

Cologne

Germany

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Acknowledgments

All the City Labs

The **NBSINFRA** project has **five city labs across Europe** that are assessing **how cities can handle different challenges and stay resilient through Nature-Based Solutions**. Each city lab aims to investigate how NBS can protect local infrastructure, preserve biodiversity, restore ecosystems and confront the challenges of climate change. The goal is to deliver tailored solutions and risk indicators for specific locations, contribute to city contingency plans and **increase the resilience and sustainability of NBS for future generations**.

Nature Based Solutions stages across City Labs

1	(Co-) Diagnosis and (Co-) Characterization Collaborative assessment of the current conditions and identification of key challenges and opportunities.
2	(Co-) Design and (Co-) Creation Co-designing and co-creating nature-based solutions with input from diverse stakeholders.
3	(Co-) Implementation Collaborative implementation of the solutions, ensuring active participation from all involved parties.
4	(Co-) Evaluation and (Co-) Monitoring Ongoing evaluation and monitoring of the solutions effectiveness through collective input and feedback.
5	(Co-) Amplification or (Co-) Replication Expanding or replicating the solutions collaboratively to ensure broader impact and scalability.

Ruse
Bulgaria

NBS stages: 1

Fingal
Ireland

NBS stages: 1-2

Aveiro
Portugal

NBS stages: 1-2

Prague
Czechia

NBS stages: 3-4

Cologne
Germany

NBS stages: 4

Visit our website for a more accurate insight on the project's city labs

www.nbsinfra.eu

Cologne

Germany

History and introduction

The city of Cologne, founded in AD50 by the Romans, is a modern city in West Germany with a population of 1.1 million people. The Rhine River flows through the centre of the city and is the focal point of the city.

Leverkusen located to the north of Cologne City, is an industrial city, and where the Wupper River empties into the Rhine. Rheinisch Bergischer Kreis with an undulating landscape gives rise to many smaller streams which are tributaries to the Wupper. Rhein Erft Kreis to the west is predominantly farmland with many smaller settlements located along the River Erft. There are multiple hazards

affecting the Cologne region. They include ever-present hazards such as Rhine River floods and hazards enhanced by climate change. Increased atmospheric heat and water holding capacity enhance hazards such as pluvial and fast moving fluvial floods in the Wupper and Erft basins, and urban heat island impacts in Cologne City.

City Lab characterisation

Ecosystems and protected areas

The City Lab's natural vegetation consist of Atlantic mixed and West European broadleaf forests of Beech, Oak and Hornbeam, historically replaced by coniferous (Spruce) plantations. Protected species in Cologne City consists of remnant hardwood and softwood alluvial Rhine forests, meadow herbs, eutrophic lake species in the north and swamp forest and heath grassland in the southeast. The Wupper Basin includes swamp forests, Alder, Ash and Beech alluvial forests and wet meadows. In the Erft Basin small sections of hardwood alluvial forests are protected.

Hazards: Floods

Rhine floods in Cologne City in 1993 and 1995 caused 70 € million and 35 € million worth of damage respectively. Heavy rainfall also caused flooding in the Wupper and Erft basins in July 2021. This resulted in rivers flowing at unprecedented levels and damage to city infrastructure, homes and businesses.

Hazards: Urban heat islands

An annual average temperature increase of 0.8°C from the 1950s means that many residents of Cologne City are living in buildings where summer temperatures now reach 35 to 40 °C with some warming greater than 40 °C.

Critical infrastructure

Human lives, homes and critical services such as hospitals, roads, electricity transformers and fire stations are all affected by hazards in the Cologne District. NBS design must avoid exacerbating damages by considering potential for maladaptation and climate change effects such as drought, pests and disease.

NBS in the City Lab

Where we already find NBS

Flood protection infrastructure in the Cologne District includes both grey infrastructure and NBS. NBS in Cologne City consist of retention basins and remnant floodplains. NBS in the Wupper and Erft basins includes retention basins along with sections of retained floodplain and riparian vegetation in the Wupper Basin. While not strictly in place for flood peak reduction, the Erft River in the Cologne district also contains four sites of meander or riverbank renaturation for natural water retention. Sites along the Wupper River are also identified for renaturation.

How existing NBS work

Floodwater retention in Cologne city is 4.5 million m³ with Worringen Bruch expected to add another 29.5 million m³ by 2027. Floodplains provide room for around 10.7 million m² floodwater before the city is impacted. Approx. 4.5 million m³ floodwater is retained in the Cologne section of the Erft basin. Only one existing (and two planned) minor retention basins operate in the Cologne Region-Wupper Basin, as several large reservoirs also retain floodwaters in the wider basin.

Location of NBS
in the Cologne
City Lab

Future prospects

NBS
interventions
for fluvial &
pluvial floods

Best practice
for green roof
substrates

Community
uptake of
green roofs

Dissemination
of best practice
to City Lab
stakeholders

Key activities

Completed activities

- Defining the scope
- Mapping ecological systems
- Analyzing the Socio-economic impact
- Documenting & mapping existing & planned NBS
- Description of existing best practice for NBS
- Documenting mitigation effects of existing NBS
- Analysis and context of natural hazards
- Mapping & characterization of local risks
- Resilience & sustainability assessment
- RSQF for Cologne City lab

Future activities

- Additional NBS for fluvial & pluvial floods
- Green roof substrates
- Increase community uptake of green roofs
- Dissemination of lessons learnt
- Sourcing data for ESA and RA
- ESA & RA for Cologne City lab

Best practices

The focus for the Cologne City lab to date has been mapping and evaluating existing and potential NBS. This information will be useful for future NBS planning by academic institutions, for authorities who are responsible for implementing and maintaining NBS infrastructure, and to illustrate to the community the benefits of and the many shapes that NBS takes.

Best practices for NBS evaluation:

- NBS can be effective in combination with existing engineered solutions (grey infrastructure)
- NBS can exist as hybrid solutions (blue/green-grey infrastructure)
- Even NBS not specifically designed for the reduction of a particular hazard can minimise hazard impacts
- Existing NBS is often silent until it is pointed out
- Technical viability is only one of the benefits of NBS
- We need to further explore the potential for maladaptation and the impact of stressors and external shocks

Best Practices for NBS mapping:

- Existing/official maps are important information sources
- To capture existing & potential NBS sites, layers must be created
- Scale will define the level of detail for display
- Landscape analysis is a precondition for identification of additional NBS sites

NBSINFRA

“Nature-based Solutions address societal challenges through actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural and modified ecosystems, benefiting people and nature at the same time.

They target major challenges like climate change, disaster risk reduction, food and water security, biodiversity loss and human health, and are critical to sustainable development.”

International Union for Conservation of Nature

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